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тиббиёт фанлари доктори, профессор,
Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт университети ректори
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Секретарь Ученого совета СамГМУ.
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3553-8727>

Шавази Наргиз Нуралиевна

DSc. доцент, заведующая кафедрой
акушерства и гинекологии N 3 СамГМУ.
<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7859-9955>

Юлдашев Рашид Захидович

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ORCID ID: 0000-0002-5409-4327

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неонатологии и протекции детских болезней №2
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ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2442-1523

Ибрагимова Малика Худайбергеновна

доктор медицинских наук, профессор
Ташкентского государственного
стоматологического института
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9235-1742

Рахимов Нодир Махамматкулович

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онкологии Самаркандского государственного
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ORCID ID: 0000-0002-3022-916X*

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*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor,
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ORCID ID: 0000-0002-5409-4327.*

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*Candidate of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor of
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Samarkand State Medical University No. 2.
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2442-1523*

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*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor,
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ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9235-1742*

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RISK FACTORS AND DIAGNOSIS OF MASSIVE OBSTETRIC HEMORRHAGE.....9
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OPPORTUNITIES OF THE OPERATIVE LAPAROSCOPY IN GYNECOLOGICAL SURGERY.....15
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USE OF RADIOFREQUENCY ABLATION IN THE TREATMENT OF PATIENTS WITH UTERINE MYOMA.....21
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GENETIC ASPECTS AND DIAGNOSIS OF CONGENITAL MALFORMATIONS OF THE GENITALS.....26
5. **Zufarova A. Shaxnoza., Eshdavlatov E. Ilkhom**
PATHOGENETIC MECHANISMS OF "EPITHELIAL-MESENCHYMAL TRANSITIONS" IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF ADHESIVE DISEASE DURING SURGICAL INTERVENTIONS IN GYNECOLOGY.....34

EXPERIMENTAL BIOMEDICINE

6. **Allahverdiyev E. Emin, Alekberova K. Chimnaz, Nasibova R. Gunel, Mammadova K. Tacli, Jafarova R. Aygun, Huseynov R. Kanan**
TREATMENT AND PREVENTION OF POSTPARTUM PARESIS.....40
7. **Verdiyeva E. Leyla, Nasibova R. Gunel, Mammadova A. Ayten, Abbasov H. Seymur, Quluyeva M. Aida**
RECOVERY OVARIAN ACTIVITY AFTER CALVING.....44
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GOSSYPOL IS A SUBSTANCE WITH UNIQUE PROPERTIES: FEATURES AND PROSPECTS FOR APPLICATION IN VARIOUS FIELDS OF SCIENCE AND PRODUCTION.....48
9. **Hikmatulaev Z. Rukhulla**
IMMUNOCHEMICAL EVALUATION OF SPINAL CORD INJURY BIOMARKER S100B IN EXPERIMENTAL ANIMAL MODEL.....57

INFECTION AND INFECTIOUS DISEASES

10. **Abduvakhitova N. Indira**
EVALUATION OF HUMORAL IMMUNITY INDICATORS IN HERPES-ASSOCIATED ERYTHEMA MULTIFORME.....63
11. **Sayfutdinov A. Zainiddin**
MICROBIOLOGICAL FEATURES OF THE COURSE OF WIDESPREAD DRUG-RESISTANT PULMONARY TUBERCULOSIS.....68

OTORHINOLARYNGOLOGY

12. **Karabayeva X. Zilola, Nasretdinova T. Maxzuna**
EPIDEMIOLOGY OF CHRONIC OCCUPATIONAL ALLERGIC RHINITIS IN FIBERGLASS WORKERS FIBERGLASS INDUSTRY.....73
13. **Nasretdinova T. Makhzuna, Xayitov A. Alisher**
MAXILLARY SINUS CYSTS, CLINIC, DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT.....78

14. **Xatamov A. Jakhongir, Amonov E. Ergashevich**
ANALYSIS OF MICROBIAL FLORA IN PATIENTS WITH COMPLICATED FORMS OF CHRONIC PURULENT OTITIS MEDIA.....84
15. **Safoeva F. Zebo, Usmanova B. Kamila, Bakiev Sh. Shavkatbek**
THE EFFECT OF GENE POLYMORPHISM ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF LARYNGOTRACHEITIS (LITERATURE REVIEW).....92
16. **Samyeva U. Gulnoza, Sabirova B. Shakhlo, Bakhranova Sh. Malika**
IMPROVEMENT OF DIAGNOSTICS AND OPTIMIZATION OF TREATMENT OF PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC LARYNGITIS.....99

RADIATION DIAGNOSTICS

17. **Dadakhanova B. Maryamkhon, KHalimova Yu. Zamira** FUNCTIONAL ASSESSMENT OF PATIENTS WITH NODULAR FORMATIONS OF THE THYROID GLAND.....105
18. **Gaybullaev O. Sherzod, Khamidov A. Obid**
THE ROLE OF RADIOLOGY IN REHABILITATION CENTERS: MODERN PROSPECTS AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS.....111
19. **Khamidov A. Obid.**
TELEMEDICINE IN REHABILITATION CENTERS: IMPROVING DIAGNOSTIC QUALITY THROUGH TELE-DIAGNOSIS.....118

MORFOLOGY

20. **Boymanov Kh. Farxod, Shukurova U. Yulduz, Allaberganov Sh. Dilshod**
MICROSCOPIC CHANGES IN INFANT LUNG TISSUE MORTALITY IN ANTENATAL PERIOD125
21. **Gaipov A. Dilmurod, Akhmedova M. Sayyora**
AGE-RELATED CHANGES IN THE FACET JOINTS OF THE LUMBAR SPINE.....132
22. **Dadakhanova B. Maryamkhon, KHalimova Yu. Zamira**
HISTO-PATHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF PATIENTS WITH THYROID NODULES ACCORDING TO THE BETHESDA CLASSIFICATION.....141
23. **Achilova U. Ozoda, Kayumov A. Abdurakhman, Mahamadalieva Z. Gulchehra**
MORPHOLOGICAL PICTURE OF BONE MARROW IN PATIENTS IN THE EARLY PERIOD AFTER ALLOGENEIC HEMATOPOIETIC CELL TRANSPLANTATION.....147

NEUROLOGY AND PSYCHIATRY

24. **Rasulova K. Dilbar**
THE ROLE OF CLINICAL AND LABORATORY PARAMETERS OF PATIENTS IN THE ACUTE PERIOD OF STROKE TO PREDICT REHABILITATION POTENTIAL.....155
25. **Muxidova X. Gulmira, Teshayev J. Mashrab**
COMPUTER ADDICTION IN TEENAGERS.....161
26. **Saidvaliyev S. Farrukh, Subkhanova Kh. Aziza**
ROLE OF ANTIDEPRESSANTS IN REDUCING THE FREQUENCY AND DURATION OF MIGRAINE HEADACHES.....165

PUBLIC HEALTH

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ANALYSIS OF TRENDS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE SYSTEM OF COMPULSORY HEALTH INSURANCE IN UZBEKISTAN.....170

ONCOLOGY

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ULTRASONOGRAPHY IN PREDICTING BENIGN OR MALIGNANT NATURE OF SOFT TISSUE FORMATIONS.....178
29. **Mamarizaev D. Yu.**
FEATURES OF MANAGEMENT AND SURGICAL TREATMENT OF MALIGNANT PHEOCHROMOCYTOMA.....186
30. **Khamrakulova N.O., Kazimov B.B.**
MODERN VIEW ON THE PROBLEM OF DIAGNOSIS IN PATIENTS WITH ANGIOFIBROMA OF THE NASOPHARYNX BY DETECTING POLYMORPHISM OF THE GSTM1 GENE199
31. **Dadakhanova B. Maryamkhon, KHalimova Yu. Zamira**
EFFECTIVENESS OF APPLYING THE ACR TI-RADS CLASSIFICATION IN PATIENTS WITH THYROID NODULES FOR FINE-NEEDLE ASPIRATION BIOPSY.....210

THERAPY

32. **Tuychieva K.Sabokhat, Tashkenbaeva N.Eleonora**
PPARG: GENETIC MARKER FOR CARDIOVASCULAR DISEASE AND METABOLIC DISORDERS.....217

TRAUMATOLOGY

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RESULTS OF ENDOPROSTHETICS IN ELDERLY PATIENTS WITH HIP FRACTURES.....227
34. **Akramov R. Vohid**
METHOD FOR PREVENTION OF EARLY DISLOCATIONS OF ENDOPROTHESIS IN PATIENTS WITH II-III DEGREE DYSPLASTIC COXARTHROSIS.....234
35. **Nuritdinov A. Ulugbek, Fattakhov A. Ravshan**
ASSESSMENT OF THE QUALITY OF LIFE OF PATIENTS WITH UNILATERAL ANTERIOR DISCLOSATION OF THE TMJ ARTICULAR DISC.....238

SURGERY

36. **Rizayev A. Jasur, Abduraxmanov Sh. Diyor**
MODERN ASPECTS OF SURGICAL TREATMENT OF VENTRAL HERNIA WITH CONCOMITANT ABDOMINOPTOSIS245
37. **Rakhmanov E. Kosim, Khamdamov D. Olim**
COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE RESULTS OF SURGICAL TREATMENT OF PULMONARY ECHINOCOCCOSIS.256
38. **Khamdamov D. Olim, Rakhmanov E. Kosim**
MODERN APPROACHES TO SURGICAL TREATMENT OF THORACIC ECHINOCOCCOSIS: EFFECTIVENESS OF MINIMALLY INVASIVE TECHNOLOGIES AND RADICAL METHODS.....263
39. **Sattarov Kh. Shokir**
CURRENT APPROACHES TO TREATMENT THE PATIENTS WITH WIDESPREAD PURULENT PERITONITIS.....268
40. **Xujabaev T. Safarboy, Dusiyarov M. Mukhammad**
PREDICTION OF COMPLICATIONS OF HERNIOPLASTY (Literature review).....276
41. **Zayniyev F. Alisher, Kurbaniyazov B. Zafar**
OPTIMIZATION OF METHODS FOR THE DIAGNOSIS OF TOXIC GOITER.....282

42. **Shonazarov Sh. Iskandar, Karimov S. Sardor**
OPTIMISATION OF TACTICAL AND TECHNICAL ASPECTS OF SURGICAL TREATMENT OF POSTOPERATIVE AND RECURRENT VENTRAL HERNIAS.....288
43. **Arziyev A. Ismoil, Sulaymanov U. Salim, Arziyeva B. Gulnora**
EVALUATION OF THE CLINICAL EFFECTIVENESS OF MINIMALLY INVASIVE METHODS IN THE SURGICAL TREATMENT OF COMPLICATIONS OF CHOLELITHIASIS.....296
44. **Arziyev A. Ismoil, Baratov B. Manon, Arziyeva B. Gulnora**
STAGE SURGICAL TACTICS FOR TREATING COMPLICATED FORMS OF CHOLELITHIASIS IN ELDERLY AND SENILE PATIENTS: EFFECTIVENESS AND RESULTS302
45. **Arziyev A. Ismoil, Nazarov N. Zokir, Arziyeva B. Gulnora**
CLINICAL ANALYSIS OF SURGICAL TREATMENT OF BILE DUCT INJURIES DURING OPERATIONS.....312
46. **Kadirov N. Rustam, Abdikadirov A. Ulugbek, Kurbaniyazov B. Zafar**
THERAPEUTIC APPLICATIONS OF MINIMALLY INVASIVE DECOMPRESSION PROCEDURES IN THE SURGICAL MANAGEMENT OF CHOLANGITIS.....321
47. **Abdikadirov A. Ulugbek, Kadirov N. Rustam, Kurbaniyazov B. Zafar Bobojonovich**
THERAPEUTIC APPLICATION OF PLASMAPHERESIS IN SURGICAL MANAGEMENT OF ACUTE BENIGN CHOLANGITIS.....330

CHILDREN SURGERY

48. **Chuliev S. Matyoqub**
PURULENT ARTHRITIS IN CHILDREN, CAUSES, CLINIC, DIAGNOSIS, PRINCIPLES OF TREATMENT.....339

DENTISTRY AND MAXILLOFACIAL SURGERY

49. **Khotamova A. Madina, Nazarova Sh. Nodira, Bahridinova R. Mohidil**
CLINICAL MEASURES AND OCCUPATIONAL HYGIENE IN THE TREATMENT OF PERIODONTAL DISEASES AND DISCUSSION OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF PREVENTIVE MEASURES344
50. **Kubayev S. Aziz, Anvarova A. Muxtasar**
ASSESSMENT OF CHEWING EFFICIENCY AND INDICATORS OF ORAL DRY METABOLISM IN CHILDREN WITH ANOMALIES OF THE MAXILLOFACIAL SYSTEM353
51. **Sadriyev N. Nizom, Musayeva A. Gulchekhra**
CLINICAL AND LABORATORY ASSESSMENT OF INFLAMMATORY PERIODONTAL DISEASES IN PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC LIVER DISEASES OF VIRAL ETIOLOGY.....357
52. **Abdurashidov A. Oybekjon**
MODERN PROBLEMS OF DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT OF ORAL CANDIDIASIS.....366
53. **Islamova B. Nilufar**
ORTHOPEDIC CASES OF ERRORS IN PROSTHETICS ON IMPLANTS.....371
54. **Anvarova A. Muxtasar**
TO EVALUATE THE ORAL MASTICATORY ABILITY AND METABOLIC PARAMETERS OF PATIENTS UNDERGOING UROPLASTY.....376
55. **Tulaganov A. Nozim**
ANALYSIS OF MAXILLARY SINUS CONDITION IN TRAUMATIC INJURIES OF THE ZYGOMATIC-ORBITAL REGION.....380

FORENSIC MEDICAL EXAMINATION

56. **Indiaminov I. Sayit, Kurmasheva K. Jamila.**
FORENSIC ASPECTS OF SEXUAL ABUSE OF GIRLS AND TEENAGE GIRLS.....391

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ZAYNIYEV Alisher Faridunovich
PhD
KURBANIYAZOV Zafar Babajanovich
DSc, professor
Samarkand State Medical University

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ANNOTATION

According to the World Health Organization, more than 750 million people worldwide are affected by thyroid pathology, with diffuse and mixed toxic goiter being the most prevalent thyroid diseases. The purpose of the study. To optimize diagnostic methods for toxic forms of thyroid disease. Materials and methods of research. The study is based on data from a survey of 112 patients with toxic forms of goiter treated between 2012 and 2023 at the multi-profile clinic of Samarkand State Medical University. Conclusions. Comprehensive preoperative diagnostics for toxic forms of goiter should include ultrasound and CT imaging. These non-invasive methods provide essential information about the size, topography, and echostructure of the thyroid gland, as well as any pathological formations. Additionally, they allow assessment of the regional lymphatic outflow zones. Radionuclide scanning is recommended for evaluating autonomous thyroid nodules, recurrent toxic goiter, and atypical thyroid localization. Hormonal evaluation of thyroid function should include measuring concentrations of TSH, T3, T4, thyroid-binding globulin, and the titer of antibodies to thyroglobulin.

Keywords: toxic goiter, research methods.

ЗАЙНИЕВ Алишер Фаридунович
PhD
КУРБАНИЯЗОВ Зафар Бабажанович
д.м.н., профессор
Самаркандский государственный медицинский университет

ОПТИМИЗАЦИЯ МЕТОДОВ ДИАГНОСТИКИ ТОКСИЧЕСКОГО ЗОБА

АННОТАЦИЯ

По данным Всемирной организации здравоохранения, «в мире патологией щитовидной железы (ЩЖ) поражено более 750 миллион человек, при этом среди заболеваний щитовидной железы пациенты с диффузным и смешанным токсическим зобом занимают первое место».

Цель исследования. Оптимизация методов диагностики токсических форм заболеваний щитовидной железы. Материалы и методы исследования. В основу исследования включены результаты обследования 112 больных токсическими формами зоба за период 2012-2023 гг. пролеченные в многопрофильной клинике Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета. Выводы. Методы комплексной дооперационной диагностики токсических форм зоба должны включать УЗИ и КТ, позволяющие неинвазивно получить информацию о размерах, топографии, экоструктуре ЩЖ и выявляемых в ней патологических образований, а также изучить состояние зон регионарного лимфооттока. Радионуклидное сканирование показано про автономных узлах ЩЖ, рецидиве токсического зоба, атипичной локализации ЩЖ. Гормональное исследование функции щитовидной железы включает определение концентрации ТТГ, Т₃, Т₄, тиреосвязывающего глобулина и титра антител к тиреоглобулину.
Ключевые слова: токсический зоб, методы исследования.

ZAYNIYEV Alisher Faridunovich
PhD
KURBANIAZOV Zafar Babajanovich
t.f.d., professor
Samarqand davlat tibbiyot universiteti

TOKSIK BO‘QOQ TASHXISLASH USULLARINI MAQBULLASHTIRISH

ANNOTATSIYA

Butunjahon sog‘liqni saqlash tashkilotining ma‘lumotlariga ko‘ra, “butun dunyoda qalqonsimon bez kasalliklaridan 750 million odam aziyat chekadi, shundan qalqonsimon bez kasalliklari orasidan diffuz va aralash toksik bo‘qoq birinchi o‘rinni egallaydi”. Tadqiqot materiali va usullari. Tadqiqotga 2012 – 2023 yy. davomida Samarqand davlat tibbiyot universitetining ko‘p tarmoqli klinikasida davolangan 112 nafar bo‘qoqning toksik shakllari bilan bemorlarning tekshirish natijalari asos qilib olingan. Xulosalar. Bo‘qoqning toksik shakllarining operatsiyadan oldingi kompleks tashxislash usullari qalqonsimon bez va undagi aniqlanadigan patologik hosilalarning o‘lchami, topografiyasi, exotuzilishi, hamda mahalliy limfa oqimi to‘g‘risida noinvaziv ma‘lumot beruvchi UTT va kompyuter tomografiyasi kabi usullarni qamrab olishi kerak. Radionuklid skanerlash qalqonsimon bez avtonom tugunlari, toksik bo‘qoq qaytalanishi, shuningdek, qalqonsimon bezning atipik joylashuvlarida ko‘rsatma bo‘ladi. Qalqonsimon bez faoliyatini baholash uchun gormonal tekshiruvlar TТG, T₃, T₄, tireoid bog‘lovchi globulin, tireoglobulinga qarshi antitanachalar tishrini aniqlashdan iborat.

Tayanch so‘zlar: toksik bo‘qoq, tekshirish usullari.

Relevance. According to the World Health Organization, more than 750 million people worldwide are affected by thyroid pathologies, with patients suffering from diffuse and mixed toxic goiter being the most prevalent among thyroid diseases [1,5,8]. Due to the persistent number of cases and the existence of endemic regions where incidence rates range from 1.2 to 9.0 per 100,000 people, thyroid diseases remain a serious medical and social issue, including in Uzbekistan, despite long-standing efforts to combat iodine deficiency [2,3,7].

At present, diagnosing toxic forms of goiter is generally not difficult, thanks largely to the development of noninvasive imaging techniques, which have an informative accuracy rate of 95-100% [6,7]. However, a lack of vigilance can lead to late diagnoses, resulting in an increase in complicated cases.

Study Objective: To optimize diagnostic methods for toxic forms of thyroid disease.

Research Materials and Methods: This study is based on the examination results of 112 patients with toxic forms of goiter who were admitted to the surgical department of the multidisciplinary clinic at Samarkand State Medical University from 2012 to 2023. Female patients

predominated—88 (78.6%) were women, while 24 (21.4%) were men. The patients ranged in age from 21 to 65 years.

Of the 112 patients, 102 (91.1%) had a first-time diagnosis of toxic goiter, while 10 (8.9%) had recurrent toxic goiter, of which 8 patients experienced a primary relapse. Out of these 10 patients, 6 had undergone their initial surgery at our clinic at different times, while the remaining 4 had a history of strumectomy at other hospitals. Postoperative recurrent goiter was identified within 5 years in 7 patients and within 10 years in 3 patients. Notably, among the 10 patients with recurrent toxic goiter, 3 initially had primary nodular nontoxic goiter, which transformed into a toxic form within 3 years, while the remaining 7 had previously undergone surgery for diffuse toxic goiter.

The extent of thyroid enlargement in patients with toxic forms of goiter was assessed according to O.V. Nikolaev's classification based on ultrasound and palpation. Results showed that 43 patients (38.4%) had a toxic form of goiter of II-III degree, and 69 (61.6%) had IV-V degree.

The severity of thyrotoxicosis was assessed according to V.G. Baranov's classification: mild in 35 patients (31.2%), moderate in 52 (46.4%), and severe in 25 (22.3%).

Based on pathomorphological form, 50 patients (44.6%) had diffuse toxic goiter, 39 (34.8%) had mixed toxic goiter, 13 (11.6%) had toxic adenoma, and 10 (8.9%) had recurrent toxic goiter.

Before surgery, patients were monitored over extended periods and received conservative therapy. Seven patients (6.2%) were treated for up to 1 year, 29 (25.9%) for 1 to 3 years, and 76 (67.8%) for over 3 years.

Results: All patients with toxic forms of goiter were assessed according to a standardized comprehensive protocol, which included a medical history and physical examination, laboratory blood tests, and instrumental evaluations.

During interviews, information was gathered about the patient's occupation, work nature, residence, complaints, symptom onset, and any family history of thyroid disease. The examination focused on neck size and deformity, eye condition, presence or absence of finger tremor, and skin condition (dryness, moisture, puffiness, pigmentation).

A nodular formation in the thyroid area, movable during swallowing and lacking cytological signs of neoplastic growth, suggested nodular goiter. The presence of multiple formations or tissue infiltration signs in the neck indicated potential thyroid cancer, requiring careful differential diagnosis.

Medical history and physical examination identified ophthalmopathy, thyroid dysfunction, and gland enlargement.

Common symptoms in patients with toxic forms of goiter included neck enlargement (44.6%), extremity tremor (63.4%), palpitations (56.2%), high blood pressure (64.3%), weight loss (48.2%), and eye changes. The severity of patients' conditions was often influenced by comorbidities. Coronary heart disease (22.3%), hypertension (20.5%), and diabetes mellitus (4.5%) significantly impacted prognosis. Among patients with toxic goiter on antithyroid therapy, a high incidence of gallstone disease (25.0%), gastric and duodenal ulcers (16.9%), chronic pancreatitis (13.4%), and chronic colonic diseases (14.3%) was noted.

Ultrasound examination of the thyroid and regional lymphatic drainage areas was performed in real time, both initially and at various points post-surgery (see Fig. 1).

Ultrasound plays a leading role in the diagnostic algorithm for examining patients with thyroid pathology, providing noninvasive, reliable information on the size, topography, echostructure of the thyroid gland, and any pathological formations. It also allows assessment of the regional lymphatic outflow zones.

Ultrasound examination was performed on all 112 patients. In 49 patients (43.7%) with thyroid tumors, a fine-needle aspiration biopsy was also conducted. The biopsy was performed without additional anesthesia, using disposable needles for intramuscular injections. The material obtained was examined by a cytologist. If follicular structures were identified in the nodules, indications for scintigraphy were given.

Radionuclide scanning and scintigraphy were performed on 37 patients (33.0%) using radionuclides ^{131}I or $^{99\text{m}}\text{Tc}$. The study was conducted using a scanner or gamma camera (scintigraphy)

to determine the position of the thyroid gland. The size, distribution contours, and intensity of radionuclide accumulation indicated diffuse or focal lesions in the thyroid gland and assessed the functional activity of nodular formations. The smallest nodular formation detected on the scan was 1 cm in size.

Fig. 1. Ultrasound of the thyroid gland. A nodular formation with a volume of up to 20 cm³ is determined in the left lobe of the thyroid gland

Fig. 2. Scanogram of the thyroid gland. Diffuse toxic goiter

Fig. 3. Scanogram of the thyroid gland. The "hot knot" in the left lobe of the thyroid gland. Toxic adenoma

Radionuclide scanning is not a screening method and was performed according to the following indications: Autonomous thyroid nodule(s) (toxic adenoma, nodular or multinodular toxic goiter); Recurrence of goiter or thyrotoxicosis after thyroid surgery; Atypical localization of thyroid tissue or thyroid developmental abnormalities (e.g., thoracic goiter, thyroid dystopia, including goiter at the base of the tongue, hemiagenesis, or agenesis of the thyroid gland) (Fig. 2-3).

Computer tomography (CT) of the thyroid gland was performed in 52 patients (46.4%) for differential diagnosis of thyroid tumors to exclude malignancies, assess the presence of primary multiple thyroid lesions, and address surgical planning. CT was useful for determining the appropriate method of strumectomy based on the stage of pathology, localization, and nature of complications [4] (Fig. 4-5).

Fig. 4. CT scan. A multi-nodular goiter.

Fig. 5. CT scan. Grade IV toxic adenoma

The hormonal function of the thyroid gland was evaluated in all 112 patients. This involved measuring the levels of TSH, T3, T4, thyroid-binding globulin, and the titer of antibodies to thyroglobulin. An elevated TSH level indicated hypothyroidism, while a decreased TSH level suggested thyrotoxicosis. Increased concentrations of T3 and T4 confirmed the presence of thyrotoxicosis.

Conclusions.

1. Preoperative diagnostic methods for toxic forms of goiter should include ultrasound and CT, which provide noninvasive information on the size, topography, and echostructure of the thyroid gland, as well as any pathological formations. These methods also allow for the assessment of regional lymphatic drainage zones.

2. Radionuclide scanning is recommended for autonomous thyroid nodules, recurrent toxic goiter, and atypical thyroid tissue localization.

3. Hormonal evaluation of thyroid function should include measuring the concentrations of TSH, T3, T4, thyroid-binding globulin, and the titer of antibodies to thyroglobulin. Elevated TSH levels suggest hypothyroidism, while decreased TSH levels indicate thyrotoxicosis. Increased T3 and T4 concentrations confirm the presence of thyrotoxicosis.

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